

Consensus ranking as a method to identify non-conservative and dissenting tracers in fingerprinting studies

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ABSTRACT

Soil erosion and fine particle transport are two of the major challenges in food security and water quality for the growing global population. Information of the areas prone to erosion is needed to prevent the release of pollutants and the loss of nutrients. Sediment fingerprinting is becoming a widely used tool to tackle this problem, allowing to identify the sources of sediments in a catchment. Methods in fingerprinting techniques are still under discussion with tracer selection at the centre of the debate.

We propose a novel method, termed as consensus ranking (CR), that combines the predictions of single-tracer models to identify non-conservative tracers. In this context, a numerical procedure to quantify the predictions of individual tracers is first delivered. The scoring function to rank the tracers is based on several random debates between tracers in which the tracer that prevents consensus is discarded. Based on these results, a conservativeness index (CI) is presented along with a clustering method to identify groups of similar tracers.

To illustrate the CI and CR procedures, an artificial mixture created with real soil to independently test the method is analysed. The results demonstrate the capability of our method to identify non-conservative tracers beyond the capability of currently used selection methods. Further, a real sediment sample from a Mediterranean mountain catchment is evaluated to emphasise its utility in complex natural environments. To test the utility of our method, it was decided to include the conservative and consensus-enforcing tracers extracted by this new approach with two different unmixing models. Furthermore, CR and CI procedures are displayed together with the most widespread statistical tests and the within-a-polygon approach used for tracer selection in fingerprinting studies. The new proposed method will enable the research community to homogenise results for replicability as well as allowing comparisons among study areas.

Keywords: sediment fingerprinting, tracer selection, consensus ranking, artificial mixture, conservativeness index

1. INTRODUCTION

Soil erosion increases fine sediment and pollutant transport into river ecosystems (Owens et al., 2005). Tracking the sources of sediment and its associated contaminants is a vital step towards mitigation (Walling and Collins, 2008; Quesada et al., 2014). It is necessary to identify the areas most vulnerable to soil erosion in order to preserve soil nutrients and land as vital resources (Quijano et al., 2016; Lloyd et al., 2019). Reliable information on sediment provenance is needed to preserve water quality and to safeguard water resources to the lowlands (Navas et al., 2009).

To evaluate this problem, several tools have been developed to quantify the effects of different erosion mechanisms, such as connectivity (Lizaga et al., 2018; Llana et al., 2019), spatiotemporal dynamics (Owens et al., 2011; Rovira et al., 2012; Wynants et al., 2020) and wind erosion (Schmidt et al., 2017; Zhang et al., 2018). However, the determination of sediment provenance in catchments using traditional monitoring techniques is frequently expensive. Thus, some preliminary work was carried out in the early 1980s showed fingerprinting techniques as key to addressing this problem (Klages and Hsieh, 1975). The procedure identifies sediment provenance and estimates the relative contribution of each potential source, using a variety of selected tracer properties.

Initial fingerprinting studies were performed based on a single tracer (Walling et al., 1979). However, the inclusion of quantitative mixing models enabled researchers to discriminate more than two sources with the subsequent increase in the number of tracers (Walling et al., 1993; Zhang and Liu, 2016). The contribution of each source is estimated using a linear multivariate mixing model. Nowadays, numerous studies use fingerprinting techniques to examine specific catchment management problems (Palazón et al., 2015; Schuller et al., 2013), to evaluate processes (Lacey et al., 2019) and contamination in the river and coastal waters (McCarthy et al., 2017; Evrard et al., 2019).

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in this technique, and for this reason, different approaches have appeared. The differences of these proposals are mainly on three

features: (a) different fingerprinting models (e.g. SourceTracker, MixSIAR, FingerPro); (b) the use of correction factors (Koiter et al., 2018); and (c) tracer selection methodologies, as can be seen in different reviews (Collins et al., 2017; Owens et al., 2016; Smith and Blake, 2014). The concern about tracer selection methodologies, including different statistical methods, has been discussed by several authors (Pulley et al., 2015; Palazón et al., 2015).

Tracer selection methods rely on the information of the sources to determine the tracer's ability to differentiate sediment sources. The most widespread methodology consisted of an initial mass conservation test, usually termed as range test (RT), followed by the two-step statistical procedure proposed by Collins and Walling (2002) that uses the Kruskal–Wallis (KW) and discriminant function analysis (DFA) tests. This procedure tests the ability of individual tracers to differentiate between sources and identifies the best combination of tracers that provides the maximum discrimination of the source classes. The main limitation of this widely used two-step statistical procedure is that it does not incorporate the information of the sediment mixtures in the analysis. Phillips and Gregg (2003) established that in a linear mixing model, the mixture sample must be within a polygon bounding the signatures of the sources as a requirement of conservativeness. More recently, following this hypothesis, Smith et al. (2013) created an R code to assess the geometry of the mixing space and to ensure that the mixture samples fit inside the sources. If a mixture sample is outside this polygon, then no physical solution exists for that mixture as one or more tracers are non-conservative. In this context, some researchers have implemented the biplot test that displays the mixture samples versus two tracers as a more restrictive condition than the traditional range test (Lizaga et al., 2019; Pulley et al., 2015).

Despite the interest of tracer selection in fingerprinting studies, to the best of our knowledge no one has studied the information provided by individual tracers in an unmixing context. Within this framework, we propose a new methodology to identify non-conservative tracers and select those with conservative and coherent information. Thus, we developed, in R code, a tool that shows the individual nature of each tracer, taking into account the information of the mixture. This study aims to independently validate the methodology using an artificial mixture

created with real soils and mixed in the laboratory. These types of samples were specifically chosen to test the method and to avoid non-geochemical sense data which increases its validity compared to virtual samples or virtually altered samples. In this research, we aim to validate the new tool by using an artificial sample and show its utility in a real study case.

In order to investigate and select the best tracers for each fingerprinting study, we propose a novel ensemble technique, termed as consensus method, which combines the predictions of single-tracer models to identify non-conservative and dissenting tracers. Based on these results, a conservativeness index (CI) is presented along with a clustering method to identify groups of tracers with similar information and to analyse their correlations. Besides, a scoring function based on several random debates between tracers, in which the tracer that prevents consensus is discarded, was implemented as a decision support ranking (CR). This novel method highlights the importance of selecting the right tracers for each individual mixture and avoids the inclusion of tracers out of consensus or with non-conservative behaviour by using both the CR and CI procedures.

2. METHODS

To illustrate the procedure of detecting non-conservative and dissenting tracers, two different datasets were selected. One dataset is composed of an artificial mixture created in the lab with real soils from three sources that included the following elements: Ba, Nb, Zr, Sr, Rb, Pb, Zn, Fe, Mn, Cr, V, Ti, Ca, K, Al, Si, and Mg. This dataset was extracted from [Gaspar et al. \(2019\)](#). The second dataset is a real example from a study case in a Mediterranean catchment that was chosen to emphasise the potential of our method for application in complex natural environments. The study case is composed of three sources. In addition, to the mentioned stable elements, gamma-emitting radionuclides, ^{137}Cs , ^{226}Ra , ^{238}U , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K and low frequency magnetic susceptibility (χ_{LF}) were also included as additional tracers. The results obtained were used to validate the method and visualise its utility.

2.1 Single-tracer model

In fingerprinting studies, measured tracer values of the sediment mixtures are usually compared to those of the sources in order to identify robust tracers that can discriminate the potential sediment sources. However, only a few of these tracers exist, requiring the inclusion of additional tracers in a composite fingerprint of poor discriminators (Pulley et al., 2017). Under this scenario, it is essential to quantify the specific information of each tracer in order to understand its contribution to the final prediction and to assist the selection of relevant tracers.

Standard linear mixing models require n tracers to determine the contributions of $n+1$ sources to the mixture (Phillips and Gregg, 2003). For example, with three potential sources and two tracers, the following system of mass balance equations can be solved to obtain the contribution of each source to the mixture:

$$AX = B$$

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad X = \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{pmatrix}, \quad B = \begin{pmatrix} b_1 \\ b_2 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \#(1)$$

$$X = A^{-1}B$$

where A contains the tracer values of each source, X represents the unknown source contributions, and B contains tracer values of the sediment mixture. The last equation of this system constrains the contributions to sum to one, requiring only two tracers to solve three potential sources.

In order to quantify the predictions of each individual tracer, we propose to use the determined mass balance equations and fabricate the remaining required tracers using two different procedures. The first method consists in designing random virtual tracers (RVT). For each tracer, a random number in the range (0,1) is assigned to each source. Then, another random number is assigned to the mixture between the minimum and the maximum values obtained in the previous step. Considering the example of three potential sources and two tracers, only one additional tracer must be fabricated:

$$\begin{cases} a_{21} = \text{random}(0, 1) \\ a_{22} = \text{random}(0, 1) \\ a_{23} = \text{random}(0, 1) \\ b_2 = \text{random}(\min(a_{21}, a_{22}, a_{23}), \max(a_{21}, a_{22}, a_{23})) \end{cases} \quad \#(2)$$

The virtual tracer is then incorporated in Eq. 1 to solve the system of equations and obtain the contribution of each source. This procedure is repeated several times, resulting in a set of solutions or density distribution that contains all the possible predictions of the considered individual tracer.

In the second method, the required tracers are randomly chosen (RCT) from the remaining ones. This technique is indicated when a high number of tracers are measured. The set of solutions obtained in this case is a subset of that obtained with random virtual tracers, resulting in all the possible predictions of each tracer in the context defined by the experimental dataset. The propagation of errors in this framework is assessed using a simple Monte Carlo iterative technique (Sherriff et al., 2015) to quantify the effect of the dispersion of the sources and the mixture on the predictions of each individual tracer.

The results from the single-tracer model can be used to define a conservativeness index (CI). The set of possible predictions from each tracer is sorted according to the Euclidian distance to the perfectly balanced mix where all contributions are equal:

$$d_i = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^3 \left(w_{i,j} - \frac{1}{3}\right)^2} \quad \#(3)$$

A percentile of the sorted solutions is chosen to compute the CI as the root mean square error (RMSE) of the non-conservative part (nc) of the apportionments from the selected solution:

$$CI = -\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^3 (nc(w_{i,j}))^2}, \quad nc(x) = \begin{cases} -x, & \text{if } x < 0 \\ 0, & \text{if } 0 \leq x \leq 1 \\ x - 1, & \text{if } x > 1 \end{cases} \quad \#(4)$$

2.2 Tracer clustering

The classification of tracers into groups requires a method for computing the dissimilarity between each pair of tracers. The results obtained by the single-tracer models are used for this purpose. This technique provides a set of solutions derived from the experimental tracer data and a series of random numbers, which are used to fabricate virtual tracers or to randomly select from the remaining tracers in the experimental database. If the same random series is used in the different models, similar tracers will show similar predictions while distant tracers will present inconsistent responses.

Correlation-based distance considers two tracers to be similar if their predictions are highly correlated, even though the values may be far apart. For this reason, the dissimilarity between each pair of tracers was computed by the Euclidean distance between the two series of predictions. The results of each pair of tracers are gathered in a distance matrix that is square, nonnegative and symmetric. We use a widely used hierarchical clustering method T based on the Ward algorithm ([Murtagh and Legendre, 2014](#)) to group the tracers.

2.3 Consensus ranking

Feature ranking is a flexible selection process commonly used in machine learning for classification problems when a large number of attributes are present in the dataset ([Hong et al., 2008](#)). This technique orders the features by the value of some scoring function to identify uninformative or redundant features which can be removed to increase the accuracy of the model. Supervised models perform this task using a curated training dataset while unsupervised models try to discover patterns in the data without guidance using self-organisation ([Solorio-Fernández et al., 2019](#)).

Several approaches can be proposed to calculate the relevance of the tracers. In this study, we focus on consensus or agreement as a criterion to identify non-conservative tracers. Consensus models have been used in Group Decision Making (GDM) to select from different

opinions of a group of people, frequently referred to as experts (Herrera-Viedma et al., 2014). Consensus reaching processes proceed in a convergent multistage way, where experts present their opinions and they discuss and negotiate to bring positions closer by modifying their initial opinions (Pérez et al., 2018). Exclusion of dissenting experts, focusing the attention where agreement is most likely, is also contemplated.

Consensus ranking (CR) is implemented combining the predictions of single-tracer models in several random debates. Debate is a technique used in Group Decision Making methods to obtain a better knowledge about experts' preferences. Experts debate and share their ideas in order to reach a common conclusion. The consensus represents a quantitative measurement of the expert agreement on the final decision (Morente-Molinera et al., 2019). In each debate, a random subset of the tracers is selected. Its number corresponds to the minimum number of equations to overdetermine the system plus one. For example, with three potential sources four random tracers are needed. In each debate, several rounds are held excluding one tracer at a time. The consensus of each round is measured through the mathematical compatibility of the resulting system of equations. The tracer whose exclusion produces a higher consensus is marked as dissenting. Repeating this process through several debates, each tracer obtains a number of participations and a number of lost debates. The consensus is simply defined as the ratio of these two numbers with possible outcomes between 0 and 100. A low consensus indicates that a tracer is often in conflict with the opinion of other groups while a high consensus represents a frequent agreement with the group.

$$consensus = 100 \left(1 - \frac{lost\ debates}{total\ debates} \right) \# (5)$$

Each debate results in an overdetermined system similar to Eq. 1 but with an additional equation.

$$AX = B + \epsilon$$

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, X = \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{pmatrix}, B = \begin{pmatrix} b_1 \\ b_2 \\ b_3 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}, \epsilon = \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_1 \\ \epsilon_2 \\ \epsilon_3 \\ \epsilon_4 \end{pmatrix} \# (6)$$

Its solution is approximated using a least squares method that minimises the sum of the squared errors (Sherriff et al., 2015), represented as ϵ in the previous equation. The consensus of each debate is measured using the RMSE of the mass balance equations.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^3 \left(\sum_{j=1}^3 a_{ij}x_j - b_i \right)^2} \# (7)$$

3. RESULTS

3.1 Single-tracer model

To quantify the predictions from individual tracers, our method incorporates the mixture information in the analysis. This knowledge may be used to predict the role of each tracer in the unmixing model and to understand how different tracers are grouped. The single-tracer model was applied to the two above described datasets.

To illustrate the results, ternary diagrams were created representing all the possible predictions from each tracer for the selected mixture. The results of the artificial mixture and the real sample are presented in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, respectively. The contribution of a source is 100% in the corresponding triangle vertex and 0% at the opposite side. Thus, each side of the triangle corresponds to a binary composition of the mixture. Moreover, a line parallel to a side of the triangle represents mixtures with constant composition in the source situated in the opposite vertex (see legend in Fig. 2). The results of the single-tracer model with random virtual tracers (RVT) are represented with blue points, and the solutions of randomly chosen tracers (RCT) are superimposed using red points. The point clouds presented in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 confirm that RCT solutions are a subset of the RVT results. Visual inspection of Fig. 1 indicates that among others Sr or Cr discriminate Source 1, while Ba or K discern Source 2 and Zn or Mg differentiate Source 3. Other tracers, such as V, Al or Si, are not parallel to a side of the triangle and require a more complex interpretation. Most of the tracers of Fig. 1 present line patterns and

some of them are narrow (Sr, K) while others are wider (Ba or Cr). The single-tracer model quantifies the effect of (a) the dispersion of the corresponding tracer in the sources; (b) the distance of the average value of the sources, and (c) the relative position of the tracer in the mixture. The results of the real sample present higher dispersion than those of the artificial mixture but linear patterns are also visible, like for instance Cr discriminates Source 1, P differentiates Source 2, and ^{137}Cs discriminates Source 3 (Fig. 2).

The conservativeness of a tracer can also be reported from the ternary diagrams, counting how many solutions fall within the triangle or, otherwise, how distant are these solutions from its centre. This property has been quantified using the proposed conservativeness index (CI) and visually assigned using a colour scale, red and black representing the less conservative tracers and yellow representing the most conservative ones. A percentile of 25% has been selected in this study so a negative CI means that at least the 75% of the solutions from the single-tracer model present non-conservative apportionments. All tracers corresponding to the artificial mixture are conservative (yellow bars) and are presented in no particular order (Fig. 1). However, tracers corresponding to the real sample exhibit a different behaviour (Fig. 2). Some of them are conservative (yellow bars) while others perform within the limit (orange bars) and the rest remain clearly non-conservative (red and black bars).

Fingerprinting studies usually mention the minimum number of tracers needed to apply an unmixing model (Eq. 1). This argument is based on the mathematical nature of the model, requiring a minimum number of independent equations to be solved. Ternary diagrams provide a visual reference of the consistency of the tracers. The intersection of their point clouds represents the solution of the corresponding system of equations. In the case of three sources, two independent tracers are needed with non-parallel lines in the ternary diagrams. This argument promotes the use of tracers with a small intersection area regardless of their individual ability to discriminate one of the sources. For instance, Rb and S from Fig. 1, could be perfectly used to unmix the artificial sample, even though its line patterns are not parallel to a side of the triangle.

The theoretical contributions of the artificial mixture are represented in Fig. 1 using a black circle. Some tracers cross this point while others remain distant. This fact illustrates that the information transmitted by some tracers, as Al or Si, may be erroneous. The causes of this deviation could be an insufficient description of the sources or the heterogeneity of the samples.

The existence of conservative tracers that could provide unreliable information, as can be seen in Fig. 1, is the evidence which motivates the consensus ranking as a necessary additional criterion. A common solution to overcome this problem is to include all available tracers in the model, expecting that errors are independent and will be cancelled. However, our approach consists in identifying and excluding the erroneous tracers in order to include in the unmixing model only those that present a conservative and consistent behaviour.

3.2 Tracer clustering

The information provided from the single-tracer model can be used to identify groups of similar tracers. These relations can be observed in the ternary diagrams where, for instance, in Fig. 1, Sr and Fe or Zn and Ti are pairs of tracers that exhibit similar patterns.

The methodology presented in Section 2.2 was applied to the two described datasets, computing first a correlation-based distance using the RVT results and then implementing a classical hierarchical clustering method. Tracers have been ordered in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 according to the cluster tree or dendrogram, also displayed in the figures under the ternary diagrams, in which the vertical axis represents the distance or dissimilarity between tracers.

The tracers from the artificial mixture (Fig. 3) are grouped in clusters mainly according to the source they discriminate. The blue branch of the dendrogram corresponds to tracers that differentiate Source 1, while the orange and yellow branches discriminate Source 2 and Source 3, respectively. The rest of the tracers are grouped in the green branch except Si that turns out to be isolated by its singular behaviour. Similar groups are found in the tracers from the real sample where only the conservative tracers have been represented (Fig. 4).

Tracer clustering is also related to the concept of mathematical consistency. Selecting tracers from the same branch will typically produce elongated intersections of the point clouds and high dispersion in the corresponding unmixing model.

3.3 Consensus ranking

The results presented in Section 3.1 indicate the existence of conservative tracers which transmit erroneous information. This statement is supported by the known theoretical contributions of the artificial mixture. Therefore, it is necessary to generalise this concept in order to study real samples where the contribution of the sources is unknown.

The notion of consensus can be illustrated with the following example. A ternary graph with the results of four tracers from the artificial mixture is presented in Fig. 5. All the tracers present line patterns and apparent conservative behaviour. However, only three of them (Sr, Rb and Ca) intersect on a small area while the fourth tracer, Al, has different intersections with each of the remaining tracers. In the case of three sources, only two tracers are needed to unmix the sample. Choosing the minimum number of required tracers from the first group of tracers will produce similar solutions while the inclusion of the fourth tracer will introduce inconsistent contribution values. The first group of tracers is compatible in the mathematical sense, or presents a general consensus on the possible solutions, while the fourth tracer is mathematically incompatible with the rest, or its specific information is out of consensus.

This example illustrates one of the random debates implemented in the consensus ranking computation in which the tracer whose exclusion produces a higher consensus is marked as dissenting. This suggests that including tracers with dissenting information does not add valuable information to the model and can lead to unpredictable results. Repeating these debates in random iterations assigns problematic tracers a low consensus rank in order to be identified as problematic and to avoid its inclusion in the unmixing model.

Consensus was calculated considering 5000 random debates per tracer for the two described datasets. Tracers are ordered in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 according to the resulting scoring, and consensus values are also presented with horizontal bar graphs. Accompanying ternary graphs correspond to the single-tracer models using RCT, as this is the information that comes into play in the random debates.

Tracers from the artificial mixture (Fig. 6) present a high correlation between the rank and the accuracy of the line patterns. The proposed ranking is able to identify problematic tracers,

that remain distant from the theoretical solution, and also to quantify differences in the variability and discrimination, visible in the thickness of the line patterns. It is important to note that these results can be considered a blind test, as the theoretical contribution of the artificial mixture is not provided during the calculus of the consensus.

When this methodology is applied to the real sample (Fig. 7), non-conservative tracers (from LF to Sr) and also tracers with high variability (^{232}Th , Mn) are assigned the lowest positions in the rank. Tracers with high consensus (^{137}Cs , Mg and P) present conservative behaviour, lower variability and higher discrimination. In comparison with the results of the artificial mixtures (Fig. 6), conservative tracers of the real sample (Fig. 7) present higher consensus values in the horizontal bar graphs. As expected, the dissenting and non-conservative tracers that are not present in the artificial sample influence these results. This highlights the importance of the resulting ranking over the specific consensus values obtained in each dataset.

The consensus calculus for the real sample was repeated discarding non-conservative tracers (from LF to Sr) from the database, obtaining the exact same rank positions for the remaining tracers. This result indicates that the proposed CR is robust and can be applied to all available tracers with no prior filtering or screening.

With the completion of the previous steps and all the information extracted, we can select the tracers that follow the general consensus. To test the utility of the new method, it was decided to include the relevant tracers (from ^{137}Cs to Rb) of the real sample in two different unmixing models: FingerPro (Lizaga et al., 2018) and MixSIAR (Stock and Semmens, 2016). Thus, the models were tested, including all the tracers that pass the range test that excludes the tracers of the sediment mixture outside the minimum and maximum values in the sediment sources. Then, RT model results are compared with those obtained for tracers selected with the CR method. As shown in Fig. 8, the unmixing results obtained after application of the CR method show more defined and accurate contributions. Furthermore, both FingerPro and MixSIAR models showed comparable results after the application of the CR method.

3.4 An improved tool for detecting non-conservative tracers

CI and CR represent an alternative to the conservativeness tests frequently used, such as the range test (RT) or the within-a-polygon approach. The RT pursued in this study removes the tracers outside the minimum and maximum values in the potential sediment sources. On the other hand, the second approach requires that the mixture samples must be within a polygon bounding the source signatures. Furthermore, this second approach needs to be done for each pair of tracers, increasing the complexity of the analysis, and is dependent on a relationship between at least two tracer properties. In addition, two selection methods, the Kruskal–Wallis H Test with a p-value of 0.05 and the DFA Test with a niveau of 0.05 were displayed together with the CI and CR procedures.

The proposed method creates a ranking of tracers suitable to select tracers based on its conservativeness and consensus rank. Furthermore, it is possible to detect those tracers with non-coherent information that could not be detected by other statistical tests. The CR methodology was implemented in the real sample dataset to show its usefulness (Fig. 9). Furthermore, these results were compared with different statistical tests and the within-a-polygon approach.

As shown in Fig. 9, different statistical tests have selected different tracers as convenient for the fingerprinting study. The selection produced by the within-a-polygon approach and the RT correlates favourably with those of the CR and CI methods. Furthermore, the tracers excluded by these two methods coincide with the lowest CR and CI values.

However, both the KW and the KW+DFA tests select as more convenient some tracers with low CR and CI values and their subsequent high dispersion and likely non-conservative behaviour. The KW test includes LF, Pb, Ba and Ti while the DFA includes Ba as selected tracers for their high discrimination of the different sources. Both methods, KW and DFA, do not use the mixture information to select the optimum set of tracers. Thus, the solutions could end up outside the physical solution space due to the relative position of the tracer in the mixture.

However, this will decrease the CI and CR values of the tracer, and the tracer would be excluded. Thus, the CR and CI approaches can effectively remove non-conservative and

dissenting tracers that pass the most widespread tests used in fingerprinting studies. These findings further support our methodology that represents a groundbreaking alternative for tracer selection methods.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 The new information of individual tracers

This work reveals for the first time the individual information or the signal that each tracer contributes to the unmixing models. This information helps to better understand the outcomes of unmixing models and to select the correct set of tracers without including tracers with non-coherent information that could lead models to erroneous and unpredicted results. Furthermore, as seen in Fig. 3, the tracers with the lowest consensus value are also classified into independent groups and present the highest error from the known solution.

This new method also aids to classify and discriminate the different groups of tracers, which is of interest to track the tracer's origin or the process to which tracers are subjected and their possible relationships. Furthermore, as a novelty, a conservativeness index is presented with a continuous numerical value, in contrast to the previous methodologies that only discriminates between conservative and non-conservative tracers.

Most of the previous studies assumed that all tracers with conservative behaviour or those selected after using the most widespread methodologies can be directly included in fingerprinting models (Collins et al., 2017; Owens et al., 2016; Smith and Blake, 2014). Our results do not confirm this hypothesis; in fact, they prove that tracers with apparent conservative behaviour but with non-coherent information in the mixture can introduce errors in the unmixing models.

4.2 The novel CR and future perspectives

In most studies identifying sediment provenance by using the fingerprinting technique, the first requirement that a tracer should fulfil to be selected for unmixing is being conservative. In this regard, Smith et al. (2018) proposed a tracer selection method to identify and remove tracers that exhibit non-conservative behaviour during transport between catchment sources and sediment sampling locations. Our results support the idea that tracer selection methodologies are

needed in order to exclude non-conservative tracers but also those with non-coherent information in the mixture. This new method shows the existence of tracers with erroneous or non-conservative information that could be selected when using the previously established tracer selection methods.

We provide a new method to identify non-conservative and non-coherent or dissenting tracers. As can be seen in Fig. 6, those tracers with lower consensus present higher errors from the known solution in the artificial mixture, thus supporting the method's capability. In addition, in the case of the real sample example, the tracers with the lowest consensus value show the least coherent information and most of their possible solutions fall outside the triangle that represents the space of the physical solution. Our findings appear to be well substantiated by the results of the two different unmixing models tested and corroborate that the tracer selection is not a model-dependent issue.

The CI procedure takes into account the information of the mixture, contrary to the traditionally proposed methods and displays a score ranking of how conservative a tracer is. Recent research has suggested the mixing polygon approach proposed by [Phillips and Gregg \(2003\)](#) as the alternative to the previously established methods for tracer selection methods. However, our findings suggest that the Phillips and Greg's method likely includes as fully conservative low-conservative or even non-conservative tracers. Furthermore, in this study, we prove the existence of tracers with dissenting information that are selected as suitable tracers by the other methods that can introduce erroneous information to the models. For this reason, the CR shows how each tracer behaves in relation to the other tracers included in the dataset and which information each tracer delivers to the model. Thus, this new method composed by the CI and the CR represents a groundbreaking alternative for tracer selection.

The CR and CI procedures represent a novel attempt that fills the gap created by the previous methodologies that are user-dependent and do not use the mixture information after the mass conservation test. Thus, without this new information, final tracer selections could incorporate dissenting and non-conservative tracers leading models to erroneous results.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The application of unmixing models is necessary to understand source-tracer relationships, which is generally performed by applying different software to select the best combination of sediment tracers. However, evidences from this study suggest that tracer selection methods are crucial in fingerprinting studies, as the use of one or another tracer could substantially modify the output of the models. Our results prove that including tracers with dissenting information produces inconsistent results. In addition, some conservative tracers could provide unreliable information and may be erroneous.

Unmixing models cannot estimate reliable contributions of sediment sources if the tracer selection procedure applied does not account for tracers with non-coherent information. Thus, in this research, we have devised an innovative methodology to identify non-conservative and dissenting tracers that enables to understand datasets and, likewise, the effect of each tracer.

The currently used methods without CI and CR information may lead to selecting dissenting and non-conservative tracers. Our study provides the framework for a new way to obtain individual tracer information to prevent the inclusion of erroneous information into fingerprinting studies.

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FIGURE CAPTIONS

Figure 1.- Ternary diagrams of all the possible predictions from each tracer for the artificial mixture. Blue and red points represent the results of the single-tracer model with random virtual tracers (RVT) and with randomly chosen tracers (RCT), respectively. The black circle located in the centre of the triangle represents the theoretical contributions of the artificial mixture with equal contribution for each of the three sources. CI values of each tracer are also represented.

Figure 2.- Ternary diagrams of all the possible predictions from each tracer for the real mixture. Blue and red points represent the results of the single-tracer model with random virtual tracers (RVT) and with randomly chosen tracers (RCT), respectively. The tracers were ordered according to the CI values, represented numerically and by a colour scale.

Figure 3.- Dendrogram plots of the ternary diagrams of the artificial sample grouped according to the source they discriminate.

Figure 4.- Dendrogram plots of the ternary diagrams of the real sample grouped according to the source they discriminate.

Figure 5.- Ternary diagram with the results of four tracers from the artificial dataset. The schematic diagram above and to the right shows how to interpret the ternary diagrams.

Figure 6.- Ternary diagrams of the results of the single-tracer model from each tracer for the artificial dataset with randomly chosen tracers (RCT) ordered according to the CR values. The black circle located in the centre of the triangle represents the theoretical contributions of the artificial mixture with equal contribution for each of the three sources.

Figure 7.- Ternary diagrams of the results of the single-tracer model from each tracer for the real dataset with randomly chosen tracers (RCT) ordered according to the CR values.

Figure 8.- Results of the unmixing procedure before and after implementing the CR and CI methods in the real mixture.

Figure 9.- Tracer selections produced by the most widespread tracer selection methods implemented in fingerprinting studies.

